

APARTHEID AND ZIONISM: THE DARK UNDERSIDE OF LIBERAL DEMOCRACY

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Abstract:

This paper examines the ideological and structural parallels between Apartheid in South Africa and Zionism in Israel, highlighting their shared roots in settler colonialism, racial segregation, and systemic oppression. Both regimes institutionalised legal and political systems that enforced racial and ethno-religious hierarchies, dispossessed indigenous populations, and weaponised law to maintain domination. Drawing on historical and contemporary evidence—including South Africa’s recent genocide case against Israel at the ICJ—the study underscores how liberal democracies have historically sanctioned exclusionary ideologies under the guise of national self-determination. By analysing land expropriation, forced displacement, and state violence, the paper reveals the contradictions within liberal democratic frameworks that perpetuate settler-colonial violence. It calls for a reimagining of democracy centred on decolonisation and justice for oppressed populations.

Keywords: Apartheid, Zionism, Settler Colonialism, Genocide, Dispossession, Liberal Democracy

In December 2023, South Africa filed an 84-page case at the International Court of Justice (ICJ) accusing Israel of violating the 1948 Genocide Convention (which was established in the aftermath of the Holocaust) during its war in Gaza. According to the document, the actions of Israel are genocidal as they intend to eliminate a substantial part of the Palestinian people residing in Gaza. The ICJ found it ‘plausible’ that Israel had committed genocide in Gaza. In November 2024, the International Criminal Court (ICC) issued arrest warrants for Prime Minister Benjamin Netanyahu and former Defence Minister Yoav Gallant of Israel, as well as a Hamas official. The ICC was of the

opinion that there are reasonable grounds to believe that Netanyahu and Gallant are responsible for crimes against humanity in the Gaza Strip from October 2023, including the starvation of civilians, intentionally attacking civilian population, murder, and persecution. In a December 2024 report Amnesty International documented how Israel during its military offensive in Gaza has carried out war crimes including indiscriminate attacks resulting in mass civilian casualties, wiping out entire families and destroying residential neighborhoods.

South Africa, like Palestine had undergone settler violence for decades under a governmental system called Apartheid. 'Apartheid' is an Afrikaans word for separateness. Apartheid was dismantled in 1994 and the first non-racial elections were held that year. South Africa established diplomatic relations with Palestine the following year. The recent Gaza war has reignited debates regarding the nature of settler colonial states and the affinities between Apartheid and Zionism.

Israel and South Africa are settler colonial states that were once supported by imperial Britain. Both these states were constituted by immigrants, and motivated by ideologies of separation and exclusivism that resulted in indigenous displacement and dispossession. Both states were products of wars that resulted in the clearing of large swaths of territory for the exclusive use of white or Jewish settlers. Both states followed broadly similar policies and practices that governed the lives of Blacks under white rule and Apartheid and Palestinians under Israeli occupation. Access to resources, particularly land, was allocated on the basis of a state-sanctioned system of racial and/or ethno-religious and national classification. As is often the case with settler colonialism, the bulk of the land was expropriated by the state (estimated 87 percent in both cases) and native access was subsequently restricted by law and the use of violence.

Like Palestinians under occupation, South Africa's white minority imposed legal restrictions on Blacks that denied them civil and political rights and spatially fragmented South Africa into Black (Bantustans and townships), colored, and white areas. The mobility of Blacks was monitored and subjected to limitations by South Africa's pass system. In Israel a parallel exists in the road, permit, and checkpoint systems. In South Africa, Blacks were subjected to forcible relocation in the service of the white-dominated economy in which they labored cheaply. In both states, law was weaponised for domination and dispossession. Dissent

and resistance were brutally suppressed with violence, physical abuse, and torture. Apartheid has been given a variety of names such as “white leadership,” “separate development,” “parallel development,” “multi-national development,” and “co-operative co-existence (Omand, 1986, p. 11).” Opponents of Apartheid see it as racism, exploitation, and domination. For Bernard Magubane apartheid is “more than mere racial discrimination or casual exploitation of one group by another, it is a strict ideology of white supremacy, racial oppression, and exploitation, whose logical extremity--genocide—is tempered by the need for African labor (Magubane, 1979, p. 250). The word Apartheid was used for the first time in 1943 in a South African newspaper (Bunting, 1971, pp. 25–26). Dr. Malan used the term apartheid for the first time in parliament in 1944 when he stated: “To ensure this safety of the white race and of Christian civilisation by the honest maintenance of the principles of apartheid and guardianship (Bunting, 1971, p. 20).” Speaking in the House of Assembly in 1963, the South African Prime Minister Henrik Verwoerd said: “We want to keep South Africa White . . . ‘keeping it white* can mean only one thing, namely White domination, not ‘leadership, not ‘guidance,’ but ‘control,’ ‘supremacy (Cherkasova, 1985, p. 88).’ Merle Lipton identified four features of Apartheid:

First, it is the hierarchical ordering of the whole social, economic and political structure of South African society on the basis of statutorily defined race. Whites (who constitute some 18% of the population) are at the top of the hierarchy; mixed-race coloureds together with Indians (roughly 12% of the total) are in the middle; and the indigenous African population (the remaining 70%) are at the bottom. Secondly, Apartheid involves systematic political and economic discrimination against all blacks, but particularly against Africans. Thirdly, it involves segregation of the races not only politically and economically, but also socially, particularly in housing and social services, including education and health care. Fourthly, Apartheid is the legalisation and institutionalisation of this hierarchical, discriminatory and segregated system(Lipton, 1987, p. 35).

Apartheid and Territorial Segregation

Apartheid was a legally sanctioned system of segregation installed by the South African National Party government in 1948 as a means to preserve white supremacy in South Africa. It institutionalised and

strengthened economic, social and political segregation between the white settlers and the native black population imposed since colonial times, and which many considered under threat as a result of economic and political development taking place in South Africa from the 1940s onwards (Posel, 1997). White economic growth and supremacy since the establishment of the modern South African in 1911 rested on the domination of less than 18 per cent of the population, which was white, over the native Africans and Indians, who constituted 82 per cent of the population. It relied on the supply of cheap black labour to the mines, cities and agricultural land owned by Whites, and the fact that black workers were not allowed to compete economically with white labour. This was made possible by restricting the Africans to the native reserves, which, by 1936, comprised 13.8 per cent of South Africa's land, and by regulating their mobility through pass laws. The South African National Party was of the opinion that the system of segregation installed since 1911 was being threatened in the 1940s as a result of South Africa's growing industrialisation and growing demands for workers in the cities and mines. This meant that many employers were turning a blind eye to illegal African workers and more Africans were illegally taking up semi-skilled jobs in white areas (Paul, 1980). The supporters of the National Party were also concerned about increasingly vocal and organised African opposition to segregation and the demands for equality in the 1940s (Carter et al., 1967, p. 30).

The ideological premise of Apartheid was based on the concept of 'separate development'. It firmly believed that races are and must remain separate, since each had and needs to maintain its own political, economic, social and cultural institutions. It relied on three key institutional pillars. The first was the legalisation of racial segregation. The Group Area Act of 1950 and other legislation classified South Africans into racial groups (black, white, coloured and Indian) and enforced residential segregation by means of forced removals to the reserves, which were redefined as Bantustans or native 'homelands'. Between 1960 and 1980, the white government forcibly displaced over 2 million people from urban areas and into the reserves. The proportion of the African population living in white areas dropped from 60 per cent in 1960 to 46 per cent in 1980 as a result of forced displacement (Freund, 1984, pp. 49-63). White state legislation also categorised the indigenous population into various Bantu, or tribal, groups. It refused to treat them

as a single ethnic or cultural entity, as political activists of the African National Congress (ANC) and Pan Africanist Congress (PAC) demanded (Carter et al., 1967, pp. 13–17).

The second pillar of Apartheid was the implementation of strict control on African labour and mobility. The Native Act of 1952, among other laws, scrapped local varieties of passes and introduced a single standard document called a reference book; for the first time, women had to carry this document, as well as all men above sixteen years of age.

This new system of control helped the state manage more directly African labour flows to urban workplaces.

Third and perhaps most importantly, Apartheid was based on the idea of separate political development for whites and for the indigenous population. The 1951 Bantu Authorities Act and the Promotion of Bantu Self-Government Act in 1959 institutionalised the residential and political separation of the natives from the whites. They sought to resolve the question of Africans' political rights by disenfranchising them from any voting rights (South Africa 1970). In white South Africa and by giving them self-rule in ten Bantustans or homelands. These were demarcated within the 13.8 per cent of the land area that had been allocated to the reserves since 1936. The apartheid architects argued that the indigenous people were ten separate 'nations', with their own languages, cultures and traditions and their own political territorial space. In 1960, Prime Minister Venvoerd stated that the government's intention was 'for the natives' people to have in their areas the same benefits in every way as for the whites in their areas - including eventual sovereign independence (Addison, 1990, p. 9). The Transkei was chosen to be the first homeland to exercise self-rule and eventual independence, as it was considered the most ethnically homogeneous and economically better endowed (Hill, 1964, pp. 15–18).

The source of authority and scope of jurisdiction of the Bantustan's parliament did not emanate simply from the indigenous population; rather, it depended on decrees and acts passed by the South African government or parliament. Economically, the apartheid regime sought to enhance the ability of the Bantustans to regulate and subsidise the cost of reproduction of the African labour supply to the white areas. In this respect, it did not seek to eliminate labour migration to white areas but rather to improve the ability of the reserves to absorb the unemployed

and poor population that had no place in the white capitalist system (Legassick & Wolpe, 1976, pp. 87-89). This was to be done by improving agricultural production along capitalist lines and away from subsistence farming, through the introduction of border industrial zones that would attract white capital while employing indigenous labour, and through financial aid supplied by the white government (Hills, Bantustans, PP. 21-36).

In 1974, after over 15 years of self-rule in the Bantustans, the white South African legislature proclaimed Bantu homeland citizenship. In 1976, it declared four out of the ten Bantustans sovereign independent states, including the Transkei.

Territorially, the Oslo agreements facilitated the 'Bantustanisation' of the West Bank and the Gaza Strip by institutionalising the fragmentation of the area. As is well known, the Oslo accords divided the West Bank and the Gaza Strip into three enclaves - A, B and C with the Palestinian Authority having territorial and civilian jurisdiction over 18 per cent of the West Bank (area A).

Racial Defense and Religious Rationale

The white South Africans see races as "static, self-perpetuating entities with fixed cultural and linguistic as well as physical characteristics, and that they themselves represented the summit of human achievement (Thompson & Prior, 1982, p. 101)." White supremacy became "a conviction deeply rooted in subconscious of all white South Africans (Cornevin, 1980, p. 20)." Marianne Cornevin argued that "the absolute superiority of the white race and the need to safeguard its political and economic supremacy are the twin cornerstones of the ideology of apartheid (Cornevin, 1980, p. 20)."

As is the case with Zionism, separation of races is central in apartheid ideology. Apartheid believes that each race is predestined to lead its own special way of life and development. Any assimilation is regarded as a violation of "purity of blood" and branded as a path jeopardising the "supreme" white race. For the "lower" race, the Africans, exposure to European culture is allegedly harmful because deviation from the primitive way of life predestined by God would result in loss of their originality (Cherkasova, 1985, p. 45).

The question of who is a white is just as important in South Africa as the question of who is a Jew in Israel. “The fact that Africans, Indians, and Coloureds have been collectively referred to as ‘non-whites’ in official terminology,” Manas Buthelezi said, “suggests that they have the identity of non-persons who exist only as a negative shadow of whites (de Gruchy, 1986, p. 158).” D.F. Malan, who became Prime Minister when the NP took power in 1948, explained:

Difference in colour indicates a simple but highly significant fact, i.e., that Whites and Non-whites are not of the same kind. They are different . . . The difference in colour is merely the physical manifestation of the contrast between two irreconcilable ways of life, between barbarism and civilisation, between heathenism and Christianity, and finally between overwhelming numerical odds on the one hand and insignificant numbers on the other (Molean, 1986, pp. 150–151).

The White perception of African inferiority goes back before the arrival of the white settlers. By the time the Dutch East India Company decided to establish a supply station at the cape in 1652, Europeans had already considered themselves superior to Africans. They tended to look down at people who differed from them “in physical appearance and social behavior(Thompson & Prior, 1982, p. 71).

The legal mechanism of Apartheid was established when the political power was granted to the white minority by the British in 1910. The constitution legalised the oppression and the exploitation of the non-white population. During the period 1934-1948, several Afrikaner intellectuals returned to South Africa with doctoral degrees from German /universities. They were “attracted by the cruder elements in German national socialism,” which emphasised “the supremacy of the nation over the individual (Thompson & Prior, 1982, p. 71).” Race purity became a central issue for Afrikaner / nationalists.

Similar to Zionism, the ideology of Apartheid is based on separation. “Hendrik Verwoerd, who was the prime minister from 1958 until his death in 1966, stated:

True unity in a racial group can only develop amongst its own people, separated from the others. The only national unity for the whites is unity amongst the whites. We do not only seek and fight for a solution which will mean our survival as a white race, but we also seek a

solution which will ensure survival and full development—political and economic—to each 1, of the other racial groups, and we are even prepared to pay N a high price out of our earnings to ensure their future . . . We want each of our population groups to control and to govern themselves, as is the case with other Nations. Then they can cooperate as a Commonwealth—in an economic association with the Republic and with each other. In the transition stage the guardian must teach and guide his ward. This is our policy of separate development. South Africa will proceed in all honesty and fairness to secure peace, prosperity and justice for all, by means of political independence coupled with economic interdependence (Thompson & Prior, 1982, p. 71).

Needless to say, the above statement does not reflect reality. We all know the plight of the Africans under the white rule as well as the plight of the Palestinians despite the nice words of the Israeli Declaration of Independence. On the South African case Leonard Thompson commented:

Like Zionism, apartheid exclusiveness is based on several religious themes.

As in Zionism, religion in South Africa has been used to justify a wide range of exploitation, discrimination, and racial policies. It has also been a dynamic force in the development of Afrikaner nationalism. George Fredrickson pointed out that

The idea that there was a divine plan to establish independent white Christian communities in what is now Natal, the Orange Free State, and the Transvaal contained the seeds of an Afrikaner nationalism that would eventually lay claim to all of South Africa in the name of ethnic and racial supremacy (Fredrickson, 1981, p. 53).

Dr. D.F. Malan, the Nationalist leader stated:

Our history is the greatest masterpiece of the centuries. We hold this nationhood as our due for it was given us by the Architect of the Universe. His aim was the formation of a new nation among the nations of the world . . . The last hundred years have witnessed a miracle behind which must lie a divine plan. Indeed, the history of the Afrikaner reveals a will and a determination which makes one feel that Afrikanerdom is not the work of men but the creation of God.

He further continued:

It is through the will of God that the Afrikaner People exist at all. In his wisdom He determined that on the southern point of Africa, the

dark continent, a People should be born who would be the bearer of Christian culture and civilisation. In His wisdom He surrounded this people by great dangers. He set the people down upon unfruitful soil so that they had to toil and sweat to exist upon the soil. From time to time he visited them with droughts and other plagues. But this was only one of the problems. God also willed that the Afrikaans People should be continually threatened by other peoples. These were the ferocious barbarian who resisted the intruding Christian civilisation and caused the Afrikaner's blood to flow in streams. There were times when as a result of this the Afrikaner was deeply despairing, but God at the same time prevented the swamping of the young Afrikaner People in the sea of barbarianism (Moleah, 1986, p. 151).

Leonard Thompson suggested that religion has been a major force in Afrikaner politics (Thompson, 1985, pp. 214, 234). W.A. de Klerk noted that "Afrikaner politics was similar to Zionist political socialisation. Afrikaner children were taught the notion of divine intervention in the creation of their nation. A boy of twelve related what he had learned:

We came here, and there was the bush, with wild grass growing. My father says the hills must have wondered who these strange people were! But we showed the hills, God had the sun smile on us. God told the skies to give us the water we needed. God asked the land to be kind to us; it took our seeds and gave us back our crops. He worked all the time, no vacations, only Sunday to pray to God. This is our country of South Africa ... We love our fatherland; and we'll fight for it, and we'll die for it (Hein, 1987, p. 22).

Like the Jews, Afrikaners consider themselves as a chosen people with a God-given destiny. They have frequently emphasised the notion that God himself placed them in Africa to fulfill a particular calling as a nation, that he gave them the Afrikaans language, and that he entrusted them with a mission to spread Christianity among the heathen.

Thus, similar to Zionism, religious themes have been central in apartheid ideology. The concepts of "chosen people," "promised land," and "children of Ham" have been used to justify white privilege and domination in South Africa. One basic feature of the settler colonialism is the notion of "vacant land." The Zionists and the Afrikaners claimed that the territories which they colonised were empty lands at the time of their arrival. South Africa was presented as a land filled with roaming wild animals when Jan van Rieijeeck built his station in 1652. In the

same line of thinking the Zionists declared Palestine to be a “land without a people for a people without land.” Ben-Gurion, the first Israeli Prime Minister, stated: “In a historical and moral sense, Palestine, the *Holy Land*, is a country without inhabitants (Moleah, 1986, p. 156).” Levi Eshkol, a former Israeli Prime Minister, asked: “What are the Palestinians (Moleah, 1986, p. 156)” Golda Meir, a former Israeli Prime Minister, declared:

How can return the occupied territories? There is nobody to return them to ... There was no such thing as Palestinians ... It was not as though there was a Palestinian people in Palestine considering itself as a Palestinian people and we came and threw them out and took their country away from them. They did not exist (Wolterstorff, 1986, p. 80).

Weaponization of Law

South Africa and Israel drew upon 19th century ideas of nationalism, culture, and race (Abu El-Haj, 2012). Israel’s first president, Chaim Weizmann, and South African Prime Minister General Jan Smuts—close associates and supporters of each other’s state-building efforts well understood the colonial nature of their projects (Stevens, 1975).

White-ruled South Africa and Israel began in the service, and as outposts, of Western powers. Each vigorously defined itself as Western and distinct from native populations (Shohat, 1999, pp. 5-20). Thus, against the will and interests of locals, ostensibly Western spaces were implanted in the heart of the Arab and African worlds. In their “promised” lands, both groups encountered a flourishing indigenous population. The “native question” in South Africa was therefore akin to the “Arab question” or the “demographic problem” in Israel.

Another important ideological parallel between Apartheid and Zionism is the fact that both states have promoted “categorical identities (Calhoun, 1994, pp. 9-36)”. Apartheid regulated social relations among Whites, Blacks, Coloreds, and Indians. Rights and the allocation of citizenship flowed from these categories and, thus, the “material force of categories appears always and instantly (Abramovitz, 1997, pp. 19-22)”. As the primary and dominant sovereign power in the Occupied Territories (OT), Israel assigns distinct legal statuses to Israelis and Palestinians residing there. Israel citizen-settlers residing in the OT have legal rights not available to non-citizen Palestinians. For example, at

checkpoints, Israeli military forces examine Palestinians' documents and permission to pass is determined by the type of identity card and/or permit they hold, while Israeli citizens, with no permit requirements travel largely unimpeded. Palestinians from the West Bank and Gaza cannot enter Jerusalem without a permit, while Israelis and Jews from anywhere in the world are free to enter the city and settle in territory still classified in the international arena as under occupation.

Among the West Bank Palestinian population, there are multiple categories of Israeli-allocated identity cards, color-coded for quick and easy assessment of rights, especially to mobility, residence, and perceived risk. In other words, the occupation divided and hierarchised Palestinians into multiple categories which were then inscribed on their identity cards: some are holders of Jerusalem residency cards, while some are West Bank Palestinian residents, others are Gaza residents, and some hold Jordanian passports. In the Israeli census, Palestinian citizens of Israel are divided into Muslim, Druze, Christian, and Bedouin, with varying rights and duties accruing to each. For example, some Bedouin and Druze serve in the Israeli Defense Forces (IDF) and, thus, are eligible for the substantial advantages and benefits that devolve from military service. "A multiplicity of hierarchically stacked citizenships" extended to Palestinians who remained in Israel after 1948, although with "curtailed" political rights and the inability to confer citizenship on non-Israeli spouses (Shafir, 2005, pp. 35-40). All Palestinians are denied the citizenship made available to Jews anywhere in the world by the Israeli Law of Return based on descent and religion.

One of the more obvious parallels between Apartheid and Israel is land policy that induced high levels of dispossession, forced migration, and population concentrations. By definition, settler colonial societies are animated by the quest for land and a vision of it as terra nullius. On the eve of the 1948-1949 war, Jews owned only six to seven percent of the land. The Absentee Property Law (1950) was the primary mechanism by which the bulk of Palestinian land was transferred to the Jewish state and/or agencies. The law gave the state the right to expropriate the land of anyone who, on or after November 29, 1947, was away from their home in Palestine for any period of time. Thus, Palestinians who fled conflict or were expelled, and subsequently denied the right of return, had their lands expropriated. Once land passes into the hands of the state or the Jewish National Fund, it cannot be sold or leased to non-Jews; it belongs to world Jewry.

Law was pivotal in South Africa's mass deportations of Blacks from one area to another as the government consolidated the Bantustans and drew boundaries in response to white farmers' desire for more land as well as to dilute the Black presence in urban areas. In one decade (1960-1970), nearly two million Blacks were displaced (Rogers, 1976). A series of laws to deprive Blacks of their resources and concentrate them in reserves and Bantustans (Rogers, 1976), date to the 1913 Natives Land Act (Washington Office on Africa 1985:). Another bill removed Blacks from urban areas. The 1936 Land Act was the basis for the allocation of land to Blacks—they were to be given marginal reserves. A series of laws, especially after the Nationalists came to power after World War II, obliged Blacks to move to Bantustans, deprived them of civil rights and compelled them to become migrant laborers (Rubin, 1981).

Each Bantustan was correlated with an ethnic or tribal group such that Swazi, for example, was the home to the Swazi, Ndebele was home to the Ndebele, Kwazulu was home to the Xhosa, Transkei and Ciskei were home to the Xhose, and so on. Bantustans were deemed “independent,” and their residents were not considered citizens of South Africa.

Resource poor and unable to support sustained agriculture, the system of Bantustans allowed the state and white capital to rely on a spatially contained pool of non-citizen Black labor. Not surprisingly, on the diplomatic front, only Israel recognised South Africa's Bantustans.

In Palestine, Zionists could not unreservedly and convincingly proclaim nativeness with a native population already present. Approximately half of the Palestinian population of over nine million people today consists of refugees, whose displacement opened space for Jewish settlement in Palestine. Today in the OPTs, Palestinians are being displaced through the imposition of untenable living conditions ultimately designed to induce ostensibly voluntary migration from rural areas to urban enclaves and abroad. As settlements proliferate in the OPT, they craft exclusivist space, expand sovereignty, and obstruct contiguous native space.

Last but not the least State repression of dissent constitutes another component of the similarities between Apartheid and zionism. In South Africa and the OT, organised resistance has been extensive and prolonged. Both the ANC and the PLO had visions radically at odds with a politics of exclusive nationalisms. Likewise, neither regime hesitated to wield violence, to obstruct indigenous rights to self-

determination, and to criminalise and demonise local political organizations such as the ANC and the PLO. Both organisations were banned and political activism suppressed. Opponents of Apartheid were labeled terrorists and communists and often legally charged as such; likewise, Palestinian militant organisations like Hamas have been deemed terrorists.

The foregoing analysis exposes the humanist pretensions of the liberal democratic ideology particularly the controversial ideologies of Apartheid and Zionism. Our notions of liberalism and democracy needs to be reconstructed from the bottom-up, taking into account the popular struggle against colonialism and imperialism. This reconstruction must begin by according struggles of oppressed nationalities against their oppressors the political dignity it deserves.

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Apartheid and Zionism: The Dark Underside of Liberal Democracy – Parwin

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